

SYNTHESIS IN ACRIDINE SERIES. PART VI. SYNTHESIS OF 5-SUBSTITUTED 1:2-BENZACRIDINE DERIVATIVES

By K. G. YEKUNDI AND S. R. PATEL

7-Methoxy-8-bromo-5-substituted 1:2-benzacridine and the corresponding 7-nitro derivatives have been described.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of 7-methoxy-8-bromo-5-substituted 1:2-benzacridine and the corresponding 7-nitro derivatives. Analogous 5-substituted 1:2-benzacridine derivatives with substituents like OMe in 7-position or Cl in 8-position and with other substituents in the attached 1:2-benzene ring have been described by Bachmann and Picha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1600). These compounds are similar in all respects to the corresponding simple acridine derivatives.

2:4-Dibromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid, obtained on bromination of *m*-methoxybenzoic acid in acetic acid solution by following the method described by Patel and Nargund (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 187), on condensation with 2-naphthylamine gave 2:2-naphthylamino-4-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid in about 30% yield. The latter was cyclised to 5-chloro-7-methoxy-8-bromo-1:2-benzacridine (I) by heating it with phosphorus oxychloride. By the reaction of (I) with appropriate amines the corresponding 5-*N*-substituted amino-1:2-benzacridine derivatives were obtained. Similarly 2-*n*-naphthylamino-5-nitrobenzoic acid, obtained on Ullmann's condensation of 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid with α -naphthylamine, was cyclised to 5-chloro-7-nitro-1:2-benzacridine (II); starting with (II) the corresponding 5-amino-1:2-benzacridine derivatives were synthesised.

(I) and (II) have been characterised by preparing their 5-phenoxy derivatives (Table I).

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2-Naphthylamino-4-bromo-5-methoxybenzoic Acid.—A mixture of 2:4-dibromo-5-methoxybenzoic acid (10 g.), fused potassium carbonate (7 g.), α -naphthylamine (7 g.), amyl alcohol (40 c.c.) and a trace of copper powder was refluxed at 140-50° for 3 hours and steam-distilled. The residual solution after filtration and on acidification furnished the product as a green powder, crystallising from acetic acid in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 220-22°, yield 5 g. (Found: Equiv., 370; Br, 21.3. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2NBr$ requires equiv., 372; Br, 21.5%).

5-Chloro-7-methoxy-8-bromo-1:2-benzacridine.—The preceding acid (5 g.) was heated at 110° for about 1½ hours with POCl₃ (20 c.c.), excess of which was removed by diluting the cooled reaction mixture with dry petroleum ether. The petroleum ether layer was removed by decantation and the residual dark thick liquid was taken up in the required quantity of acetone. The acetone solution was poured in a thin stream in a well-stirred ammonia solution containing ice whereby the product

separated out as a fine green powder. It was collected and washed with excess of water. It crystallised from toluene in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 240°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 3.6. $C_{19}H_{11}ONClBr$ requires N, 3.7%).

2- α -Naphthylamino-5-nitrobenzoic acid was obtained by condensing 2-chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid (9 g.) with α -naphthylamine (6 g.) in a similar way as the 4-bromo-methoxy analogue. It crystallised from acetic acid in greenish yellow powder, m.p. 247-49° (decomp.), yield 4 g. Its potassium salt was sparingly soluble in hot water, from which it crystallised as yellow needles. (Found: Equiv., 309; N, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires equiv., 308; N, 9.1%).

5-Chloro-7-nitro-1:2-benzacridine (II) was obtained from the above acid (5 g.) by heating it with $POCl_3$ (20 c.c.) by following the method described before. It crystallised from toluene in orange needles, m.p. 252-53°, yield 3 g. (Found: Cl, 11.7. $C_{17}H_9O_2N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.5%).

TABLE I

(B denotes -1:2-benzacridine)

	Name.	Method.	Shape.	M.P.	Formula.	% N	
						Found.	Calc.
1.	5-Phenoxy-7-methoxy-8-bromo-B	From (I) & phenol.	Greenish yellow powder.	172°	$C_{24}H_{16}O_2NBr$.	3.3	3.2
2.	5-Amino-7-methoxy-8-bromo-B	From (I) & $(NH_4)_2CO_3$.	Do	291-95°	$C_{16}H_{13}ON_2Br$.	7.67	7.9
3.	5-(γ -Morpholinopropyl)-amino-7-methoxy-8-bromo-B	From (I) & γ -morpholino-propyl amine.	Yellow granules	270° (decomp.)	$C_{25}H_{26}O_2N_3Br$.	8.5	8.7
4.	Dihydrochloride of (3).	...	Yellow powder	295-97° (decomp.)	$C_{25}H_{24}O_2N_3Cl_2Br$.	7.4	7.5
5.	5-Phenoxy-7-nitro-B	From (II) & phenol.	Greenish powder	165°	$C_{21}H_{14}O_3N_2$	7.8	7.6
6.	5-Amino-7-nitro-B	From (II) & $(NH_4)_2CO_3$.	Orange powder.	298-300° (decomp.)	$C_{17}H_{11}O_2N_2$	14.9	14.5
7.	5-(β -Diethylamino- α -methylbutyl)-amino-7-nitro-B	From (II) & β -diethylamino- α -methylbutyl amine.	Yellow granules	228-30° (decomp.)	$C_{26}H_{32}O_2N_4Cl_2$	14.2	14.5

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